

Impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Economics Concept Among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Economics Concept among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and research hypotheses. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consists of a total number of 17,057 SSII students offering economics in all the twenty-two senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, during the 2024/2025 academic session in Katsina State. Purposive sampling technique was employed in this study to select A total sample size of 216 SSII students Economics Performance Test (EPT) was used as an instrument for data collection which was adopted from senior secondary school examinations past question papers 2019 and 2022 West African Examination Council (WAEC) and 2021, 2022 and 2023 National Examination Council (NECO). For the validity of EPT, the instrument was subjected to face validation through consulting three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.89. Mean and standard deviation were used to present demographic information, while independent sample t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of confidence. Findings from the study revealed that students exposed to concept mapping instructional strategy, performed better in Economics concept than those who were exposed to lecture method. The study concluded that, teaching using concept-mapping instructional strategy is more effective in teaching Economics concepts than using the conventional method of teaching. The study also recommended among other that Economics curriculum planners, policymakers and economics teachers should consider adoption of concept mapping as an instructional strategy in economics education, given its proven effectiveness in improving students' performance.

Keyword: Concept Mapping, Instructional strategy, Economic Concept.

Introduction

Education has been described as a vital and indispensable key to any form of development. It is an instrument for economic, political and scientific development of all nations (Offiah, Achufusi, 2010 & Olarinoye, 2001 and Otuka, 2006). This could be the reason why the Federal Government of Nigeria emphasized the teaching of social sciences (Economics inclusive) in its National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013). A major challenge in teaching is to create experiences that involve students and support their own thinking, explanation, evaluation, communication and application of scientific models needed to make sense of these experiences (Afolabi & Akinbobola, 2009). Social Science Education always considers learner-centeredness in teaching and learning situations as strong strategy which fully involves students to take charge of their learning. (Aminu, 2019).

This development has generated lots of attention related to understanding how learners learn and how to help them learn about concepts. He posits that these efforts have helped learners to learn more effectively and have also led to the development of meta-cognitive strategies to enhance meaningful learning among them. More so, one of the aims of secondary education is to equip students to live practically and effectively in this modern age of Science and Technology (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). To this end, students at the senior secondary level of education are required and expected to study one Social Science subject like Economics as a prerequisite to the pursuit of courses such as Accounting, Economics and Business Management at the university level. This paves the way for Economics to have a unique position in the school curriculum.

Economics is a social science that studies human behaviours in their efforts to allocate scarce resources efficiently and effectively in order to minimize cost in a given environment (Amaechi, 2014). It is one of the subjects that are offered in the senior secondary schools in Nigeria. According to Hansen in Oleabehle (2014) Economics is one of the few social science

subjects that heavily utilized statistical and mathematical models to analyze real-life socio-economic problems. The relevance of economics as a requirement for technological advancement of a nation cannot be underrated. Economics, as a subject, helps to develop in the learner skills such as analyses, experimentations, manipulations of variables and making decisions which are very important in socio-economic investigations.

However, the level of achievement of the objectives of Economics at secondary school level could be determined by the students' performance and retention of its subject matter. Performance, according to Hornby (2001) is academic accomplishments of students as a result of exertion of efforts, skills, perseverance and practice. It is the degree or level of success attained at the end of an academic endeavour (Iwundu, 2001). Corroborating this view, Uroko (2010) posits that academic performance of an individual is learning outcome of that particular individual. This includes knowledge, skills and ideas acquired and/or gained through a course of study within and outside classroom situations. Performance explains educational efforts of the students (Ugwoke, 2014). The author further reiterates that it refers to the level of success made in an academic endeavour. Performance in education could be related to academic success recorded by a learner in the teaching and learning process. It could be seen as the success students make in their academic pursuit.

Students' performance in economics depends on the teaching methods and strategies employed by teachers of the subject in Nigerian secondary schools (Aniodoh, 2001). Some of these methods include both teacher-centred and learner-centred pedagogies respectively; they consist of discussion, demonstration, discovery, inquiry, problem-solving and lecture methods. However, in spite of all these strategies and methods adopted by most Economics teachers during classroom engagements with their students, their level of performance in the subject is not encouraging. Indeed, it is not appreciable, particularly if these students are to offer programmes in Economics at the tertiary levels of education. Aniodoh (2001), reasons that the consequence of students' general poor performance in Economics in our secondary schools derives largely from the teachers' employment of conventional lecture method in teaching the subject. The author submits that this method is purely teacher-centered; the teacher dominates all burning issues in the subject while students remain passive listeners, copying notes given by the teacher during classroom sessions. Oleabhiele and Ikumelu (2012) disclosed a number of challenges countering effective teaching and learning of Economics at the secondary school level as follows: general display of negative attitudes among both teachers and students; the unwieldy nature of economics curriculum; use of irrelevant instructional materials by teachers; a prevalence of too many topics to be covered in the subject; and inadequate periods allocated for Economics education in schools. The researcher also posits that in a bid to cover the unwieldy syllabus in economics, teachers indulge in the employment of traditional teaching strategies such as lecture method which involves mostly the cognitive domain of learning at the expense of affective and psychomotor domains. In almost the same vein Adamu (2010) disclosed other reasons for poor performance of students in Economics among which are: (a) use of inadequate teaching methods by teachers; and (b) students' poor attitudes of learning the subject. Moreover, in spite of the traditional teaching methods and strategies employed by the Economics teachers, students' performances at various levels continue to decline. Hence, the foregoing lapses of the conventional method of teaching in curriculum delivery necessitated the search for effective teaching/learning strategies suitable for improving the performance and retention of Economics students among senior secondary schools. This brings about the employment of an innovative teaching-learning strategy such as concept-mapping which can be used for effective teaching of Economics concepts and therefore leading to meaningful learning.

Concept-mapping is an innovative teaching-learning strategy that could be used for effective teaching of the sciences as well as social sciences in the task of creating forums for meaningful learning. Concept-mapping constitutes a product of recent advances and new philosophy of sciences. Contemporary perspectives of cognitive psychologists and new philosophers of science on cognition view learning as an active process of construction where the learners' prior knowledge plays significant roles in conceptual learning (The American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), 2014). The technique of concept-mapping constitutes a means of representing the emerging science knowledge of students. It depicts a hierarchy and relationships among concepts.

A concept map is a two-dimensional representation of the relationship between key ideas. At first glance, a concept map looks like a flow chart in which key terms are placed in boxes connected by directional arrows when based on educational psychology theories of how we organize information, concept maps are hierarchical, with broader, more general items at the top and more specific topics arranged in a cascade below them (Ajaja, 2013). Adamu (2010) also, revealed that conscious efforts were being made to determine suitable strategies that could facilitate effective learning and understanding of Economics concepts among students at the senior secondary school level. He emerged with the view that one of these strategies considered requisite and appropriate by scholars and experts (Cliburn, 1990; Wood, 2000; Aniodoh, 2001; Marangos, 2003; Cardellini, 2004; Butcher, 2006; Novak & Canas, 2006; and Yusuf, 2009, cited in Sale (2019).

In facilitating effective learning and understanding of Economics concepts at the level of senior secondary education is rooted in the exploration and employing the assets established in concept-mapping as a teaching strategy. These frames of thought by Adamu (2010) were the major reason that prompted the researchers into attempting to determine the impact of concept-mapping instructional strategy as a teaching method and design that could foster improved academic performance and retention of economics concepts among senior secondary school students. The afore-mentioned scholars and teachers generally concede that concept-mapping is a learning strategy that could motivate learners to learn by motivating their interest in solving economics tasks. Novak and Gowin (1984) cited in Rabe (2018) posits that a standard concept map construction method includes the following series of steps: (i) Defining the topic; (ii) Listening the most important concepts; (iii) arranging concepts hierarchically; (iv) adding links to form a preliminary concept map; (v) adding linking phrase; (vi) adding cross links; and (vii) Reviewing the map.

The researchers have expressed concern on how many students in secondary schools struggle to learn economics concepts and social science related subjects and most often do not achieve success through their learning as a result of teachers' attitude of employing conventional teaching methods in economics. However, some instructional methods and strategies commonly adopted in Nigerian senior secondary school system only encourage rote -learning at the expense of meaningful learning. The existing instructional practices do not actively involve students in the learning process but rather, render them as only passive listeners and seems to prevent them from taking charge of their learning. Other factors could stem from students' failure to construct or develop appropriate understanding and perspective of the fundamentals of Economics concepts through the learning strategies exposed to them during classroom pedagogy. This development has generated amongst students a number of factors considered antithetic to learning and mastering Economics concepts including the following; demonstration of negative attitudes, display of loss of interest and lack of commitment and attention in the class during Economics teaching. This scenario has left many students with poor performance in both public and internal examinations.

In spite of the high expectations entertained by stakeholders in our secondary schools about the need for students to perform credibly in Economics in both public and internal examination in the Nigerian schools' system, it is disheartening that the employment of approaches and strategies which are designed for effective teaching and learning of economics in the task of promoting and committing learners in embracing classroom practices and activities tailored for enabling them achieve mastery and retain concepts taught in the subject are not being put in-place in most classrooms. In most secondary schools, behavioural practices prevail where the students remain passive while the classroom environment is mostly teacher-dominated. However, in recent, different teaching-learning strategies, including concept-mapping teaching strategy, have been evolved and developed to accelerate the learning process amongst students. These new teaching-learning strategies are deliberately designed to necessarily commit the roles of the teacher, students and curriculum content conjointly in any given teaching-learning situation. Additionally, these attempts are tailored at promoting learner-centeredness in classroom pedagogy. He advances that in economics the new approaches are meant to shift teaching from behaviourism to constructivism in order to enhance conceptual learning in the subject apart from involving students in their own knowledge construction, and placing them at the center of their learning activities while the teacher is considered as a facilitator.

Thus, the recent emphasis on the exploration and employment of concept-mapping as a teaching strategy has brought new tools for making students go beyond rote-learning, because it is an effective teaching strategy that has become extensively used in teaching many subjects. The concept mapping helps learners to externalize their thinking in visual and verbal forms to improve their understanding of learning apart from allowing them to extract important information that bear on a variety of ideas and represent them in a structured manner. To the best of researcher's knowledge and understanding, very little research has been done to empirically establish the extent to which the impact of concept mapping strategy in Economics teaching could bring about improvements on students' academic performance, and retention among economics students. This motivates the researcher to fill in this research gap by investigating the impact of concept mapping instructional strategy on students' academic performance and retention in Economics among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate Impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Economics Concept among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the impact of concept mapping instructional strategy on students' performance in Economics when compared to students taught the same subject using lecture methods among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.
2. Ascertain the difference in academic performance between male and female students taught Economics using concept mapping strategy among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered to guide the study:

1. What is the impact in the academic performance between students taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method among senior secondary schools in Katsina State?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance scores between male and female students taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy among senior secondary schools in Katsina State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

1. There is no significant impact in academic performance of students taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture methods among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.
2. There is no significant difference in academic performance of male and female students taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

Various empirical literatures relevant to the present study were reviewed as follows:

A study conducted by Onuoha, Ejimonye, Eneogu, & Ugwuanyi (2016) titled 'Effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Students' Achievement and Interest in Economics in Secondary School in Enugu Education Zone Enugu State, Nigeria'. In the study, Quasi-experimental study of non-equivalent Pre-test, Post-test control group design formed the research design. Hence, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. 282 students from intact classes from four secondary schools randomly drawn in Enugu Education Zone were used as sample for the study. The main instruments for the study consisted of Economics Achievement Test (EAT) and Economic Interest Inventory (EII) which were developed, validated and used for data collection. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions and further used Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to further test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the above study shows that students that were taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy performed better and had higher interest mean score of 3.28 than their counterparts taught with the lecture instructional strategy that had a mean score of 2.90.

A study conducted by Kizilgol, Kilic & Abdioglu (2016) titled: "The Effects of using the Concept Mapping and the Traditional Method on the Academic Achievement of Students in Learning the Fundamental Topics of Cost Accounting" The study is based on a quasi-experimental pattern with a matched Pre-test-post-test control group. The sample group was distributed to the observation (concept mapping) group and the control (traditional method) group as twenty-eight students for each group. The differences between the pre and post-tests' score averages revealed that the observation group performed better as the score averages of the observation group decreased less than that of the control group (0.68<3.00). The results show that the concept mapping is more effective on the academic achievement and performance levels of the participating students. Therefore, this study is reinforcing the affirmative effects of using concept mapping as a method of teaching and learning cost accounting and other areas, by emphasizing the increase in students' learning achievements and the level of meaningful learning.

A study conducted by Dorji (2020) titled: "Effect of concept mapping strategy in teaching and learning economics and academic performance in higher secondary school" The study was carried out with 35 students of class eleven at one higher secondary school under Thimphu Thromde, Bhutan. In this study, mixed methods were adopted. However, quantitative data was collected through the Autumn class test (pre-test) and class test (Post-test). The Pre-test and Post-test data were analysed and interpreted via descriptive statistics through mean, standard deviation, and inferential statistics via t-test and level of confidence and statistical significance. The qualitative data collected through observation of group works and presentation, and group reflective journals were analysed by coding and thematic analysis was drawn to analyse the data. The findings depicted that students have a positive opinion towards concept mapping. The mean difference between the class test and the Autumn class test was 17.18. This shows that concept mapping has a positive impact and using it systematically could improve teaching and learning Economics.

Similarly, a study conducted by Ruma and Abdurrahman (2024) titled: "Impact of Concept Mapping on Academic Performance of Males and Females among Secondary School Physics Students in Katsina State, Nigeria" A total number of 91 students from a public secondary school in Katsina Education Zonal Quality Assurance was purposively selected from a population of 3,968 science students, using simple random sampling technique. This study adopted pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research designs. Two groups were formed: Males and Females group. Both groups of students were taught Motion concept via Concept Mapping strategy. The instrument used for data collection was Motion Concept Performance Test (MCPT). The instrument was validated by both Physics teachers and some selected lecturers in the field of chemistry education

unit. The reliability coefficient of MCPT was 0.79. The statistical tool used was Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient in order to determine the reliability coefficient of MCPT, this study was guided by a research question and answered using descriptive statistics. The researcher tested the null hypotheses at 0.05 significant level of confidence via statistical tool t-test statistics. The results obtained from data analysis shows that the mean academic performance score of male students is 31.79, while female students in the same group have a mean score of 31.85. This shows that both male and females students taught motion concepts using concept mapping Strategy have almost similar mean academic score in their post-test indicating that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students exposed to concept mapping teaching strategy in motion concepts.

Cofie, Sarfo and Doe (2021) Conducted research titled: “Teaching and Learning of Genetics Using Concept Maps: An Experimental Study among Midwifery Students in Ghana” The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of using concept maps to enhance the teaching and learning of genetics among midwifery students. This study adopted an experimental study using the pre-test/post-test control group design. Meanwhile, fifty-one (51) midwifery students (females) in Ghana were voluntarily recruited and randomly assigned into either experimental or control groups using a ‘balloting method. However, in the Pre-test phase, the groups were first administered a Genetics Achievement Test (GAT) to measure their understanding of basic genetic concepts. The experimental and control groups received two (2)-weeks of lessons in genetics using concept mapping and lecture methods respectively during the intervention phase. Following the intervention phase, a Post-test (GAT) was administered a week after the intervention to determine whether concept-mapping as a teaching strategy significantly improved the learning and achievement of students, where data analysis was done via JASP software (Version 0.14.1). The results however revealed that there was no significant difference in GAT scores between the groups during the Pre-test phase, ($t = 0.763$, $df = 45$, $p = 0.194$, $d = 0.214$). However, the experiment group performed better in the GAT than the control group, ($t = 9.402$, $df = 45$, $p < .001$, $d = 2.634$).

A study conducted by Chiou (2013) titled: “Effects of Concept Mapping Strategy on Business and Economics Statistics Learning Performance” The purpose of this study was to help students relate and distinguish differential statistical concepts. A single-factor, between subjects experimental design with three participant groups (collaborative concept mapping vs. individual concept mapping vs. Traditional exercises) was employed. The experimental results suggested that adopting concept mapping strategy can significantly improve students’ statistics learning achievement compared to using traditional exercise method, and adopting collaborative concept mapping can better improve students’ achievement than using individual concept mapping. The findings of the study based on achievement post-test showed that the average mean score of the control group was 50.82, the individual concept mapping group was 65.65, and the collaborative concept mapping group was 79.29.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design to investigate the impact of concept mapping instructional strategy on students’ academic performance in economics among senior secondary schools in Katsina State. However, pre-test, post-test and post-post-test were used for experimental and control groups. This design was employed because students were not randomly assigned to groups. According to Gall, Gall and Borg (2007), quasi-experimental design can be used when it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the subjects and assign them to treatment groups without disrupting the academic programme of the school involved in the study. Two research questions were raised, while two null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

The study was conducted in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study comprised all 17,057 SSII Economics students in 22 senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Quality Assurance (ZEQA) of Katsina State for 2022/2023 academic session (Source: ZEQA, Department of Planning Research and Statistics, Katsina, 2023). The sample size for the study was 216 Economics students in two intact classes from two senior secondary schools sampled for the study. The two senior secondary schools were selected from the 22 senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance through purposive sampling technique. Economics Performance test (EPT) was used for data collection from the samples. EPT is a multiple-choice objective test adopted from NECO; 2021, 2022, 2023 and WAEC 2019 & 2022 Economics past question papers to measure students’ performance on the topics covered during the study namely: demand and supply, production possibility curve, basic cost concepts, market structures, industrial concepts and theory of income determination.

The instrument was face validated by three experts. One from curriculum unit, one from Measurement and Evaluation unit, Department of Education and one from Department of Economics. All in Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria. To obtain the reliability coefficient (r), Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used. The reliability index of 0.89 was obtained which was considered high enough for the study. Data were analysed using

mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while T-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

Regular Economics teachers of sampled schools were used in the experimental section to reduce the effect of teacher variability that could have affected the outcome of the experiment. The researcher played the role of monitoring the regular teachers to make sure the experiment was properly conducted. However, the researcher trained the regular Economics teachers to control the effect of teacher variability in the experiment. The training was done using the concept mapping instructional strategy lesson plan (CMISLPs) and the lecture instructional strategy lesson plans (LISLPs) to guarantee similarity of instruction during the treatment.

To minimize students' interaction that could have affected the results of the experiment, the researcher informed the regular Economics teachers not to give the students any assignment in the process of the experiment. Intact classes were used for the experiment, so there was no randomization of the research subjects. However, t-test was used in data analysis to reduce the effect of pretest on posttest. The experiment was conducted for six weeks. This period is deemed long enough as to reduce pre-test effect to post-test achievement.

Results

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in academic performance of students taught economics using concept mapping instructional strategy and the students taught the same subject using lecture methods among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

Table 1: T-test Analysis on the Mean Difference between Performance Scores of Students Taught Economics Using Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy and those Taught Using Conventional Method

Comparing Pairs	N	X	SD	T	Df	P-value	Decision
Concept Mapping	117	27.27	2.902	10.762	214	.000	Rejected
Conventional	99	22.86	3.105				

Analysis done at: 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed).

The result in Table 1 indicated that there was a significant difference between concept mapping (M=27.27, SD=2.902) and conventional method (M=22.86, SD=3.105) in their economics academic performance; $t(214) = 10.762, p=0.000$. This was because the calculated p-value= 0.000 is less than alpha-value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that "There is significant difference in academic performance of students taught economics using concept mapping instructional strategy and the students taught the same subject using conventional methods among senior secondary schools in Katsina State" is hereby rejected. Hence, the experimental group perform better than the control group.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in academic performance of male and female students taught economics using concept mapping instructional strategy among senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

Table 2: T-test Analysis on the Mean Difference between Performance Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Economics Using Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy

Gender	N	X	SD	T	Df	P-value	Decision
Male	73	27.55	2.863	1.322	115	.189	Accepted
Female	44	26.82	2.943				

Analysis done at: 0.05 level of significance (2-tailed).

The result in Table 2 indicated that there was no significant difference between male (M=27.55, SD=2.863) and female (M=26.82, SD=2.943) in their economics academic performance; $t(115) = 1.322, p=0.189$. The result is insignificant because the calculated p-value= 0.189 is greater than alpha-value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in academic performance of male and female students taught economics using concept mapping instructional strategy among senior secondary schools in Katsina State" is hereby retained.

Discussion of Findings

Result from the first hypothesis (table 1) revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students who were taught economics using concept-mapping instructional strategy (experimental group) and those taught the same subject using conventional method (control group). The difference was found to be in favour of the

experimental group. Therefore, this denotes the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result is in agreement with that of Onuoha, Ejimonye, Eneogu, & Ugwuanyi (2016) investigated the Effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Students' Achievement and Interest in Economics and discovered that students that were taught Economics using concept mapping instructional strategy performed better and had higher interest mean score of 3.28 than their counterparts taught with the lecture instructional strategy that had a mean score of 2.90. The finding of this is also consistent with Kizilgol, Kilic and Abdioglu (2016) examined the Effects of using the Concept Mapping and the Traditional Method on the Academic Achievement of Students in Learning the Fundamental Topics of Cost Accounting discovered that the differences between the pre and post-tests' score averages revealed that the observation group performed better as the score averages of the observation group decreased less than that of the control group ($0.68 < 3.00$), showing that the concept mapping is more effective on the academic achievement and performance levels of the participating students. Also, Dorji (2020) investigated the effect of concept mapping strategy in teaching and learning Economics and academic performance in higher secondary school and discovered that students have a positive opinion towards concept mapping. The mean difference between the class test and the Autumn class test was 17.18. This shows that concept mapping has a positive impact and using it systematically could improve teaching and learning Economics.

Result in table 2 indicated that, there was no significant difference between the performance of the male students taught Economics using concept-mapping instructional strategy and the female students taught using the conventional method. Therefore, this denoted that the null hypothesis was retained. The result supports the work of Ruma and Abdurrahman (2014) that discovered that the mean academic performance score of male students is 31.79, while female students in the same group have a mean score of 31.85. This shows that both male and female students taught motion concepts using concept mapping strategy have almost similar mean academic score in their post-test indicating that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students exposed to concept mapping teaching strategy in motion concepts. This finding was also aligned with the work of Cofie, Sarfo and Doe (2021) who examined Teaching and Learning of Genetics Using Concept Maps: An Experimental Study among Midwifery Students in Ghana and discovered that intervention to determine whether concept-mapping as a teaching strategy significantly improved the learning and achievement of students. This revealed that there was no significant difference in GAT scores between the groups during the Pre-test phase, ($t = 0.763$, $df = 45$, $p = 0.194$, $d = 0.214$). However, the experiment group performed better in the GAT than the control group, ($t = 9.402$, $df = 45$, $p < .001$, $d = 2.634$). Finally, the concept mapping instructional strategy is recommended as a powerful teaching approach for genetics as a topic in midwifery studies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that using concept mapping strategy in teaching the concepts of economics improve students' performance better than the use of conventional. The findings also demonstrate the efficacy of concept mapping instructional strategy in improving the performance of economics students and highlight its potential as a valuable tool for teaching and learning economics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Economics curriculum planners, policymakers and economics teachers should consider adoption of concept mapping as an instructional strategy in economics education, given its proven effectiveness in improving students' performance. This will also give them an opportunity to participate in, for a more comprehensive learning process that is very relevant to the professional practice requirements.
2. Government through teacher training institutions should provide teachers with training and development opportunities to learn how to effectively design and implement concept mapping strategies in their economics classrooms so as to facilitate teaching and learning.

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